

Narrative review: Food packaging using nanotechnology in fruits and vegetables

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Abstract: Food, horticulture, agriculture, and food science are among the industries that are using nanotechnology more and more to preserve fruits and vegetables. Cost and inadequate shelf-life improvement are two disadvantages of conventional approaches. By extending these products' shelf lives, nanotechnology can reduce manufacturing and post-harvest losses. Because of their special properties, nanoparticles are important in food packaging and storage as they improve food quality and lower the rates at which oxygen, water vapour, and relative humidity are transmitted.

Keywords: *nanotechnology, nanocoating, fruits and vegetables, food preservation, shelf life, nanoencapsulation*

1. Introduction

Nanotechnology is the scientific approach of producing or using materials having structures smaller than 100 nano meters. Because nanotechnology is a new and developing technology, this technique can be shown to have a simulative effect when combined with existing techniques. The function of nanotechnology begins with the creation of a product and ends with its sale in the food sector. Foods developed with the use of nanotechnology during growth, processing, and packaging are known as nano foods.

The term "nanotechnology" was first applied in 1974 by the late Norio Taniguchi of Tokyo University, when he described material development at a nano meter scale (Paredes, Asensio, Llabot, Allemandi, & Palma, 2016). Although they are often referred to as construction materials, this term is frequently used to describe their design, characteristics, manufacture, and use. Since that time, their focus has moved from materials to devices and systems. Nanotechnology has been used to describe the design and manufacturing of materials, gadgets, and systems that can be precisely dimensioned at nano meters.

In nanotechnology, size and control are at the heart of it (Ramsden, 2016).

The word "nanotechnology" is not just used for food. The many other present procedures and industrial sectors can be revolutionized with the aid of nanotechnology. It may be used in industries including medicine, food safety, environmental research, healthcare, and communication technology, among others. Future times will call for novel and inventive goods and methods. Nanotechnology is a new and practical approach in the food industry is nanotechnology. Research and development of nano technological packaging for food products as well as monitoring are currently very important in the food business (Wesley et al., 2014).

Packaging history

Food packaging has changed from being only a container for holding food to something that may now actively influence the quality of the food. In three diverse situations, packaging serves three main purposes: communication, usefulness, and protection. The settings are natural, evocative, and built-up. A package should be optimized such that it can do all three roles, particularly in each of the three contexts (Risch, 2009).

Three thousand five hundred years ago, glass was used to package food in Egypt. Later, mulberry bark containers were used in China, and Napoleon campaigned for canned goods. Metal printed boxes were the first packaging material utilized in the history of metal packaging in the United States in 1866. Later, in 1959, the first aluminum-can food was introduced. In recent years, there have been substantial improvements to food packaging. Nanotechnology, often known as nano-packing, is a

cutting-edge method that has been used in food packaging for food safety.

2. Nanotechnology in the food industry

Nanotechnology applications are now widely used in the food business and significantly impact every element of this industry. Nanotechnology provides tools and methods for addressing food safety issues such as the detection of microorganisms or toxins, prolongation of shelf life at mealtime, and advances in packaging (Bajpai et al., 2018). Nanotechnology approaches to food safety focus on the antibacterial potential of nanoparticles and nano sensors for the detection of pathogens such as faecal coliforms and pollutants (Nasr, 2015).

In food safety, nanotechnology is helping to identify poisons, allergies, and pathogens. In addition, it is used for inhibiting bacterial biofilms on the surface of foodstuffs and food contact surfaces. It facilitates the improvement of food packaging that includes biotechnological, eco-friendly edible packaging. Nanoparticles and composites made from polymer-based materials are the ideal solution for this task, using nanotechnology in food packaging.

Silicon dioxide and titanium dioxide are the most frequently used nanomaterial's in food packaging. Silicon dioxide is used as an anticaking agent, drying agent and food coloring agent in the preservation and packaging of foodstuffs. It helps absorb water molecules and also has hygroscopic properties (Pradhan et al., 2015). Nanoparticles of titanium dioxide have been used as food coloring and photo catalytic disinfectants. Additionally, they can be used to whiten dairy goods like milk and cheese. In food packaging, titanium dioxide often acts as a UV barrier. Even in large numbers, these two nanoparticles can be employed as food additives. This method makes it simple to integrate nano supplements into meals to improve nutritious components (Mohammad et al., 2022).

Nanotechnology in fruits and vegetables

Fresh produce is an important source of nutrients and bioactive chemicals that are good for human health. Due to

their brief shelf life and high perishability after harvest, these products suffer sizable worldwide losses. Fruit and vegetable post-harvest losses have been decreased with the use of cutting-edge technologies like nanotechnology. Nanotechnology can be used in the creation of edible coatings with increased qualities for increasing produce shelf life, packaging with antimicrobial activity enhanced by physical barrier properties and sensors that detect internal quality and ripening stages of fruits and vegetables (De Oliveira Filho et al., 2022).

Nanocoating

According to customer demands, processing has recently been less necessary in goods as the market favors fewer significant changes in the features of food articles to preserve their functional and nutritious qualities. To achieve this objective, the food surface is treated with a nanomaterial coating that extends its shelf life and maintains the quality and usefulness of foodstuffs. Edible coatings may be added to food products by rubbing, submerging, or spraying them. In the manufacture of these coatings, eco-friendly components are used to a large extent. Furthermore, the food additives should have been removed prior to consumption in certain circumstances. Nanocoating is a tiny layer of surfaces that ranges in thickness from 1 to 100 nm (Yousuf et al., 2018).

Fresh food items like fruits and vegetables continue to oxidase even after being picked since they take up all the oxygen in the environment. Conversely, edible coating produces CO₂ instead of oxygen, which cannot escape the layer and leaves residue in the final product. The process then transitions to partial anaerobic respiration, which uses 1-3 percent less oxygen. The manufacturing of ethylene is hampered by the lower oxygen availability. Moreover, there is a reduction in the loss of water from the body's physiology resulting in enhanced firmness and 2 times greater shelf life for fruits and vegetables. For a wider range of time periods, they remain healthy and fresh (McHugh and Senesi, 2000).

Nanocoating is a quick method for coating perishable goods, such as fruits and vegetables. Wax covers a wide variety of

fruits, such as apples, tomatoes, citrus, and others. The wax coating is intended to improve the food's look while minimizing the flow of water vapor and oxygen. The fruits are covered with food-grade wax (Kumar Raghav et al., 2016).

Nan laminates

Thin films are also nano laminates. Food-grade ingredients are stacked two or more times to create these. The films can comprise a variety of antioxidants, antimicrobials, and antibacterial chemicals. These additives aid in extending the product's shelf life. Layers can be created using a variety of materials, including polysaccharides and phospholipids.

Due to the high moisture content of fresh produce, there are several biological activities. Fruits and vegetables include nano laminates to reduce biological activity and lengthen shelf life. The primary basis for the usage of edible laminates in agriculture is the post-harvest methods used to address the issue of microbial development during transportation (Acevedo-Fani et al., 2017).

Nano sensors

Nano sensors are the tools used to evaluate the quality of food products. Nano sensors help with the issues of food packaging (Mohammad et al., 2022). Consumers may be confident in the products they are buying thanks to nano sensors. To preserve food safety, the use of nano sensors helps to lower the frequency of food-borne illnesses. Nano sensors are nothing more than nanoparticles with pathogen-detecting properties. The mechanical or chemical sensors known as nano sensors are employed to identify certain physical or chemical properties. In the food industry, nano sensors are utilized to attain the appropriate level of sensitivity (Shawon et al., 2020).

Nano biosensors

Nano biosensors are mostly utilized in the pharmacological and food industries. In the food division, multi-enzymatic sensors are employed to determine sucrose levels. When monosodium glutamate is produced, glutamate concentration

is measured using glutamate sensors. The microbial sensors known as "ethanol sensors" measure the concentration of ethanol during the fermentation process of alcohol (Zamora Sequeira et al., 2019).

3. Active packaging

Active substances are included in the matrix of frequently used packaging materials using the technology of active packaging. For the integration, techniques including immobilization, coating, sachets, or pads are used. Food that is packaged actively changes in condition. The food that is packaged inside the packaging material is altered by the active packaging.

Active packaging consists of two main components:

A. Nano-based antimicrobial packaging

Packaging material and food contact materials integrate antimicrobial nanoparticles such that the packaging itself acts as an antibacterial in response to changes in the microbial, humidity, and many other altering variables. Nano scale zinc oxide, nano scale chlorine oxide, nano scale magnesium oxide, nano scale copper oxide, carbon nanotubes and nano scale titanium oxide remain the most often utilized nanoparticles. In the future, carbon nanotubes are expected to be used in antimicrobial food packaging (Bumbudsanpharoke & Ko, 2015).

B. Oxygen-scavenging material

Food degradation is caused by indirect oxygen contact, which primarily refers to food spoiling caused by aerobic microbes. Commercial oxygen scavengers are sold as sachets that include metallic or inorganic reducing agents like iron oxide, ferrous carbonate, etc (Rooney, 2005).

4. Intelligent packaging

The main goal of food laws is to ensure the safety of food. Physical characteristics, sensory qualities, microbiological safety, and nutritional value of the food are the major factors

that maintain quality control in food products. The communication function of conventional food packaging is extended by intelligent packaging, a subset of smart packaging (Yam et al., 2005).

5. Indicators

Indicators for the time and temperature- These indications are used to show whether someone has been exposed to too much heat. Additionally, it keeps an eye on the state of the food product as it is being produced. The products' exposure to changing temperatures is tracked by these sensors. These sensors display temperature-dependent irreversible changes in physical attributes, shape, and colour.

Indicators of freshness- Commercially, freshness indicators are employed in intelligent packaging to show the product's quality. Freshness indicators focus on colour changes of the indicator tag brought on by the presence of microorganisms that cause deterioration.

Integrity indicators or indicators of leakage- To monitor the integrity of the package during manufacture and delivery, leakage indicators are affixed to the packaging (Ghaani et al., 2016).

6. Future of nanotechnology in food packaging

Food science and technology can benefit greatly from the growing topic of nanotechnology. Additionally, it is crucial to the packaging process. Nanotechnology-enhanced food packaging provides superior antibacterial and physical barriers that extend the product's shelf life. The application of nanotechnology in food packaging reduces the interaction between gasses and moisture. Nanoparticles have been used in food processing to enhance nutritive value, flow characteristics, flavor, colour, and stability or to increase shelf life (Wesley et al., 2014). These are used to enhance the taste, flavor, and shelf life of the food products. The newest technique is nanoencapsulation which is potentially used to protect sensitive food ingredients from various environmental factors. The interest in nanotechnology is increasing day by

day. Along with the need for food safety and quality, nanotechnology in food packaging is in high demand nowadays. Nanotechnology will have benefits in all types of industries. In the future, nanotechnology will be crucial in the realm of food science and technology (Thakur & Modi, 2020). Food makers' primary concern is food safety, which nanotechnology can help with (Park, 2007).

Nano packages are used to influence the shelf life, texture, and flavor of the products. Different indicators can be used to detect leakages, food pathogens, extension in temperature etc.

7. Nanoencapsulation

Nanoencapsulation (NE) is a method which is used to pack in tiny amounts and give the finished product substance functionality such as controlled release of the core. The use of pharmaceutical products made with non-food grade ingredients is not acceptable for incorporation into foods as food applications of nanotechnology for target delivery of bioactive (e.g., omega-3 fatty acids, carotenes, vitamins, coenzyme Q10, plant polyphenols, etc.) Are still in their infancy (García et al., 2010).

In order to facilitate the distribution of desirable bioactive substances through the food supply, research in food-grade encapsulates is required. Nanotechnology derived foods are also new to consumers, and it remains unclear how public perception, attitudes, choice, and acceptance will impact the future of such applications in the food sector (Chaudhry et al., 2008).

The food business is likewise seeking innovative technology to boost the nutritional content, shelf life, and traceability of their products. They are also aiming to develop improved tastes, reduce the amount of salt, sugar, fat and preservatives, address food-related illnesses and develop targeted nutrition for different lifestyles (Sekhon, 2010).

8. Nano toxicology

Nan toxicology studies the environmental impact of nanoparticles, which are smaller than 100 nm and have

distinct optical and electrical properties. They are utilized in a variety of industries, but their high surface area and uncoordinated surface atoms make them hazardous (Raman, 2021).

The least concerning are foods or nano foods that are broken down or dissolved in the digestive system. Foods containing non-bio permanent nano materials that are not broken down but are instead transported by the gastrointestinal tract are of moderate concern. The key issue is that nano foods contain indigestible, insoluble, and bio permanent nano additives are a cause for worry.

Effects of nano toxicity

The important mechanism of nano toxicity is the generation of reactive oxygen species i.e., ROS. The overproduction of ROS can cause oxidative stress and cells fail to maintain normal physiological functions. Nano toxicity can also lead to DNA damage and can initiate cancer. When humans are exposed to nano materials, the cells allow them to pass through the cell membrane. Then nanoparticles affect the functions of cells. Many of the nanoparticles are commercially synthesized like iron oxide, and zinc oxide nanoparticles having commercial applications such as personal skin and hair repair products, coatings, paints etc. Nano zinc oxide and nano titanium oxides which are produced commercially cause major harmful effects on human health.

9. Conclusion

The food business is using nanotechnology increasingly to preserve and package fruits and vegetables. It enhances the packaging's resistance to gasses, moisture, and microbes. While active packaging modifies product conditions, nano sensors aid in the reduction of food-borne illnesses. Additionally, nanotechnology improves taste, flavor, and shelf life in nutritional supplements and nutraceuticals. Changing colour, texture, and sensation also enhances production and processing methods. The use of nanotechnology in the food

business is anticipated to increase despite certain drawbacks in the industrial, health, and pharmaceutical sectors.

10. References

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